

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT DYSFUNCTION

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Abstract

Occlusal disorders are of great importance in the etiology and pathogenesis of the TMJ dysfunction syndrome [1]. Stabilizing factors next to the intraarticular disc, ligamentous-capsular apparatus, muscular corset is occlusion - multiple, symmetrical, point fissure-tuberos closure of the dentition [2].

Therefore, any violation of functional occlusion can lead to negative changes in the functional state of masticatory muscles, dispositions of the lower jaw, disorders of intra-articular relationships and anatomical safety of its elements [3.4]. It is obvious that the combination of endocrine and psycho-emotional pathologies that affect the level of adaptive capabilities of the body to adverse conditions, violations of functional occlusion are the trigger for the development of the pain syndrome. Treatment of patients with TMJ dysfunction should be comprehensive, phased and include drug therapy, physiotherapy, orthopedic methods: treatment with caps, selective grinding of teeth, rational prosthetics [5].

Keywords: TMJ dysfunctions, functional occlusion.

Purpose of the study: based on the data of anamnesis and clinical and laboratory studies of patients, to establish the causes leading to the appearance of occlusion-articulation syndrome of TMJ dysfunction and to outline a set of orthopedic dental measures for the treatment of the above pathology.

Material and research methods.

The clinical examination included the collection of complaints and anamnesis, as well as a detailed functional examination - facial examination, cephalometry, checking the mobility of the lower jaw, palpation of the masticatory muscles, clinical examination of occlusion. For a more detailed examination of the nature of the closure of the dentition in the position of habitual occlusion,

anterior and lateral, articulation features were studied on diagnostic models of the jaws in an articulator debugged for individual work.

Results and discussion.

We examined 22 patients (16 women, 6 men) aged 19 to 47 years with symptoms of TMJ dysfunction. Pain syndrome of varying strength forced the patients to seek help. Patients complained of unilateral or bilateral pain in the parotid-masticatory region with irradiation to the temple, jaws, teeth, cheekbones, headaches, earaches. As a rule, patients were emotionally aroused, seeking help - they were nervous, crying, emotionally depicting their feelings.

During the examination of 22 patients with the syndrome of pain dysfunction of the TMJ in 8 persons

(30.8%), violations of functional occlusion were established for the following reasons:

- increased abrasion of hard tissues of the teeth against the background of parafunctional activity of the masticatory muscles, which led to a loss of occlusal height, the appearance of unstable occlusal contacts in position

- central ratio, supracontacts during laterotrusive, protrusion movements of the lower jaw; TMJ dysfunction; deformities of the occlusal surface of the dentition due to carious destruction

- and partial loss of teeth. Disturbances in articulatory balance led to the movement of the teeth towards the existing defects, and therefore, to the appearance of supracontacts in the central occlusion;

- errors in the process of orthopedic treatment, namely: fixation on prostheses of the previous usual forced position of the jaws, formed as a result of violations of the functional occlusion and disposition of the lower jaw that existed before prosthetics; incorrect formation of the occlusal surface of artificial crowns and bridges, the appearance of unstable occlusion, supracontacts;

- errors of orthodontic treatment. Change of occlusal relationships led to dispositions of the lower jaw and intra-articular disorders.

Patients were treated in several stages. At the first stage, the pain syndrome was eliminated by creating conditions for relaxing the masticatory muscles. To eliminate the pain syndrome, a complex of therapeutic measures was used: medication, physiotherapy and

treatment with caps. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory and analgesic drugs (Meloxicam, Ketanov) were prescribed, including in the form of ointment dressings in the parotid-masticatory area based on ibuprofen, butadione, 5% Diclak gel. As part of complex therapy, calcium, iron, vitamins of group B, C, folic acid were prescribed, which affect the metabolic processes of nerve and muscle cells, eliminate tightness and soreness of muscles, which reduce the irritability of trigger points.

To relieve psycho-emotional stress, improve sleep, sedative preparations of plant origin were prescribed. Physiotherapeutic procedures included massage, myogymnastics, impulse current, electro-, ultraphonophoresis for 10-15 procedures.

To relax the muscles, deprogramming their work at the first stage, relaxation plates with clamp fixation and a bite pad behind the upper incisors were used. The bite pad behind the upper incisors was in contact with the lower incisors, creating deocclusion of the lateral teeth by 1-2 mm, which helped to turn off the effect of the supracontacts of the contacts on the forced position of the lower jaw, relax the muscles and self-center the articular heads in the articular fossae.

It was recommended to wear the plate for two weeks (to avoid protrusion of the lateral teeth), constantly, always at night. The plate was corrected after 1, 3 days, 1, 2 weeks. Patients indicated a decrease in pain and tension in the masticatory muscles after a few days. At the second stage, the central ratio of the jaws was determined and fixed. After knowing the pain syndrome, it became possible to find and fix the "healing, comfortable" position of the lower jaw for the TMJ, which does not depend on the existing occlusal contacts, but is limited by the anatomical shape of the TMJ, its connected-capsular apparatus. To determine the central ratio, manual techniques were used, including the orientation of the lower jaw during swallowing movements.

To fix the central ratio, bite plates made of refractory Aluwax wax, thermoplastic plates, occlusal A-silicone, and in the absence of a large number of teeth, hard bases with wax bite ridges were used. At the third stage, the lower jaw was fixed in the "treatment" position with the help of stabilizing, repositioning caps.

After determining and fixing the central ratio of the jaw model, they carefully studied in the articulator, planned and carried out selective grinding of the teeth, and made burl structures. Stabilizing caps covered the occlusal surface of all teeth and provided point contact only with the supporting tubercles of the opposite jaw.

The anterior teeth were in contact with the cap only when the teeth were strongly compressed. In the area of the lateral teeth, the cap had an occlusal thickness of 1.5-2 mm. On the cap, "fangs guidance" was created during laterotrusion, contact of the incisors during protrusion movements of the lower jaw, while excluding contacts of the lateral teeth.

Such design features of the stabilizing splints contributed to muscle relaxation and self-centering of the articular heads in the physiological position.

According to the integrity of the dentition, the mouthguards were mainly made for the lower jaw, since it had advantages in aesthetics, phonetics, and

was easier to manufacture. In the absence of teeth on one jaw, the mouthguard was installed on the jaw with defects in the dentition, while it took the form of a mouthguard-prosthesis. Quite often, the choice of jaw for the installation of a mouth guard depended on the inclination of the upper incisors. Along their vestibular edge, an inclined mouthguard was installed on the upper jaw, which made it possible to reproduce the functional surface on the mouthguard and provide an effective sagittal incisive path with a gentle start of movement of the lower incisors along the palatal surface of the upper jaws and deocclusion of the lateral teeth.

The period of use of caps depended on the improvement of the patient's condition, and on average ranged from 2 to 6 months.

For dispositions of the lower jaw, reposition caps were used. With deep imprints of antagonist teeth on the occlusal surface made it possible to keep the lower jaw in the "treatment" position.

At the fourth stage, after effective therapy with caps, it was carried out. Planned prosthetics with the reproduction of the morphology of the occlusal surface of the dentition on the prostheses and the normalization of occlusal relationships in the central occlusion. Often, the final prosthesis was preceded by temporary structures, on which the occlusal relationships were corrected.

Conclusions

1 According to our observations, in about 30.8% of patients

Syndrome of pain dysfunction of the TMJ revealed violations of functional occlusion.

2 The cause of violations of occlusal relationships is the pathological processes of the dentition, their morphological and functional complications, as well as iatrogenic factors

3 Violation of functional occlusion on the endocrine and background background of psycho-emotional pathology leads to the emergence of a syndrome of pain dysfunction of the TMJ.

4 Treatment of patients with occlusion-articulation syndrome of TMJ dysfunction should be complex, multi-stage and include drug therapy, physiotherapy, treatment with caps to normalize occlusal relationships and the functional state of masticatory muscles, rational prosthetics.

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THE USE OF DENTAL IMPLANTATION IN THE TREATMENT OF A GENERALIZED FORM OF PATHOLOGICAL ABRASION OF TEETH, COMPLICATED BY DEFECTS IN THE DENTITION

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Abstract

The article describes the treatment that was carried out in a complex manner, taking into account the general state of health, the age of the patient, the activity of the course of the pathological process by restoring the anatomical shape of the teeth and replacing defects in the dentition with orthopedic structures based on dental implants. Dental implantation in the area of dentition defects was performed in the presence of a sufficient amount of bone tissue and no indications for bone augmentation. During the first month after implant installation, a decrease in stability in the “bone-implant” connection was noted, then, in the second and third months after the operation, an increase in implant stability with the achievement of maximum performance in a year, which indicates remodeling of the bone tissue around the implant.

Keywords: pathological erasure of dental hard tissues, dental implantation.

The gradual loss of hard tissues of teeth throughout the entire period of existence of the human body is a natural process that is the result of the physiological function of chewing and non-chewing movements of the lower jaw. There are two types of abrasion of hard tissues of teeth - physiological and pathological. Physiological erasure is considered as a process that prevents functional overload of periodontal tissues and provides physiological movements of the lower jaw in various phases of articulation. Physiological abrasion of hard tissues of the teeth proceeds gradually, and normally, before the age of 40, only the first visual signs of physiological abrasion appear in the form of loss of enamel within the dentin.

Pathological abrasion is designated as a rapidly progressive pathological process, accompanied by a pronounced loss of enamel and dentin, aesthetic, phonetic and functional disorders of the dentoalveolar system. According to the indications of the loss of hard tissues of the teeth, three degrees of pathological abrasion are distinguished: I degree - erasure of hard tissues within the enamel, partly dentin; II degree - erasure of hard tissues of the teeth within the main dentin (without translucence of the tooth cavity); III degree - erasure of enamel and dentin within the replacement dentin (with translucence of the tooth cavity) and IV degree - erasure of the entire crown of the tooth. According to the prevalence of the pathological process - limited and generalized

clinical forms of pathological abrasion [1]. among which dental implantation has become increasingly popular in practical dentistry over the past 20 years. To date, the state of dental implantation is characterized by high efficiency and a significant range of possibilities. According to the literature, due to the successful development of structures, the improvement of the technology of manufacturing materials and methods of surface treatment, the level of successful osseointegration of installed dental implants reaches 90–98% [2, 3]. At the same time, issues of prevention of complications of dental implantation are of great importance. associated with functional overload, characteristic of pathological abrasion and bruxism, which leads to a reduction in both their service life and the period of use of orthopedic structures based on dental implants, which determines the relevance of the study.

Materials and methods of research

A clinical and laboratory examination was carried out in 72 patients with generalized pathological abrasion of hard dental tissues aged 35 to 65 years, 39 women and 33 men. , determination of the size and topography of defects in the dentition, the state of hard tissues of the teeth, the height of the clinical crown of the teeth, the state of periodontal tissues and alveolar processes, the type of bite and occlusal relationships, the state and position of teeth that have lost antagonists, the presence of dentures in the oral cavity, the duration